

97. Nāgiriḱaṇḱa, between Mahādiulwaewa and Minhettigāma in Kadawat Korle Nuwara Kalāwa, 5 miles east of the central road at the 103rd mile post from Jaffna near the village Issembessaewa on a hill. Wihāra destroyed. The old name of the place was Bamanogiriya as can be seen from the inscription I. line 2, and II. line 3 and 5; it is not mentioned anywhere in the historical books. At I., line 1, we find mentioned the Rukkha-wawiya (*see above* No. 58) and Welunaka, but, unfortunately, only two lines are legible. No. II. has five lines of which the last three are very well preserved; the beginning of the inscription is destroyed. The subject of the whole is as usual about tanks and we meet here for the first time with the expression wawisara, modern wāesara, a composition analogous to candramāsa. In the second line we find mentioned the Bariyawawisara, the Cadagiriyawawisara and the Būmawawisara, none of which I can identify, and in the last line we have the Karakaṭa already known from Habarane (No. 61).

98. Galkowila, at Karagaswaewa, about 5 miles west of the 29th mile post on the road from Kurunaegala to Anurādhapura. This inscription begins Nakamaharajaha puta and then follows the name of the king, which is not quite legible on the stone. The inscription is beautifully preserved and the form of the characters leaves no doubt that it must be later than the fourth century, although there is hardly any change in the language; but this is quite natural if we assume that a certain terminology was fixed for such inscriptions which remained in use for several centuries.

99. Nayinnawella wihāra, in Waegampattu, Wellassa, $1\frac{1}{2}$ miles South of Bibile, a village 36 miles from Badulla, on the new road to Batticaloa. The inscription is on a flat rock about 50 yards from the temple, and appears very well when the sun shines on it. Some letters, however, are destroyed in the last three lines and the end is missing altogether. No king is mentioned in the inscription, but at line 4 the ancient name of the place Nakala wihāra is given, and this is most probably identical with the Nakalanagara mentioned at Mah., p. 142.*

100. Galmaduwa, at Ambogaswaewa, about 4 miles from Meḱiyāwa (N.W.P.). Inscription on a large rock near to a small tank a little above the temple, tolerably well preserved but very incorrect, so that nothing can be made out of it. The subject seems to be as usual tanks and paddy fields. The end is evidently wiharahi sagasa dine but in these three words alone there are four mistakes.

101. Nayindanāwa wihāra, 2 miles from Mā Eliya, a village on the new cross road from Kepiṭiyāwa to Dehelgomuwa (N.W.P.). There are two inscriptions, one in a cave in older characters and with the usual contents, and one on the cliff face over the wihāra in characters of the fifth century. I give this

* The present Sinhalese name is Muhunnaru or Mūnaru under which it is mentioned at Mah. 68, 48.

mi Padana (9) galida me warahata pawatara na uyuta koṭu sa (10) padinaka catara sahasaka kiri ce me di aca (11) nani nawa sahasaka kiri yaha ugu wama (12) carita niyamina rajakolihi bhaṇana (13) mini mewa baka kari di catara anaṇa beda (4) baka ca sesika . . . tawa na (15) Padana galihi buka saga hamiyana ca [ta] (16) ra pacayada uwayutu karawani koṭu apa cu (17) di purumukaha dina niyamani me ca sali (18) hi liyawaya dinamaha.

77. Piliḡāma.—Siddham. Uṭarata Mahagawaṭagama aṭa sahasayata wara kaṇa yama raṭayahi iṭa toṭa kawara ca (2) mahaka jetakaha iwa awasesa balaha iwa caka raṭa pāyahi abala watuka awaraṇaga . . . ma tera karahi (3) haha . . yana wihara atani semana aṭa arakata koṭu caka kariha caka amaṇata kubara haṇa raṇa wiharahi ma (4) habikasaganata catara pacahata dinamaha.

85. Diyaḡāma.—Siddham mahakaḡaka mada wada [ra] (2) upasakuya i ya pita iwa wadāra caraka pita i (3) jabu caraka iwa yaya toṭa kubare pata iwa ṇa jabu ḡaka iwa (4) caka kari dasa tiku kubara.

97. Nāḡirikaṇḡa.—(a.) Sidha, Weḡunaka rukawawiya tana meliya kaḡo tejo jisa koṭasahiwika koṭasaka Bāmānogiriya weherahi saga

(b.) ṭa mama parumaka sakata puta ha Bamanogiriya wehera ḡayo kino wenadaka dawaka mahabariye (2) wawisara kanugariya wawisara kabuba (?) wawisara kaṭinaka-pulasara (3) wawa sama satara wawisara dakapati kaṇaya badipita Bamanogiriya wihara bikasangahata caka (4) paca yaṭa dine saga бага kariya kama atanā samita wa awiwa nila sawiwa . . gaṭa awiwa kahawana (5) wataka wawi daka pata . . bojapata . . Bamanogiriya wihara bikasaga dini pita karakataka saga sari.

98. Galkowila.—Siddham. Manaka maharajaha puta Bata Tisa ma (2) haraja manana (?) karihi paca caliwata hamudata keta (3) Wihirabija wawiya . . rukawawiya ceta ha wana Abalayaha ceta karihi (4) bojiya pati karakata ya kubare wiharahi tela mala ceta (5) . . jinapatisatarahi koṭu dine.

102. Wellangolla.— bikasaganata . . . kahi rukawawi haka kubara . . . wadara iwa bikasawi . . niyata iwa (2) Bayawawiya wi iwa maraduwaya . . . iwa mahatawi iwa me ceta kubare (3) karanā kahi

110. Malākalattaewa.—A. Siri saṅg boy ma purmukā pasalošwanne nawayae pura dasa wada Pāṇḡi rad Dāpuḡu warae mekaḡ par ha kureḡi senim isā nawa turāe saṅḡim isā mahale Dāpuḡā arak samaṇan warae kuḡa salā daḡ siwim isā kolpatrī saṅḡa aetaḡu wae aep me tuwāk deṇaḡo eḡ sewae wadaḡeyin Sen mahā

B. lāeṇan tuman māeṇian nāemin nam di koṭ karana lad Nāl-aran meheṇi warhi tuman tuḡu wat sirithi se dawaspata mahaweherae mahaboyae diy waḡā waḡi meheṇi wat haembu

done (even) by himself, at the wihāra of Caityagiri and at the rock temple of Ambasthala, having made offerings of oil and flowers at the Gapa caitya which extends over a karīsha, having repaired the decayed buildings at the Copatalaya, Giniya, and Gapacaitya, he handed them over to the monks of the Lord of the world, and after having assigned he gave them the Karakaḷa tank. At this caitya he gave it; after having assigned 1020 karīshas, and to the sons of the minister Wahabaya in the Puwayasa Sawanaka year on the seventh day in the bright half of the month Majimodini.

(67.) Slab from Tissamahārāma:—Hail! We, Buddhadāsa, Mahinda, Mahāsenā, three brothers, the great king Abhaya and our uncle the parumaka Buddhadāsa, a venerable, reverend therā, [declare]: King Jeṭṭha Tissa, our sire, bought the karīshas belonging to the villager Toda and remitted the taxes; 9,000 karīshas from Padanagala were given to the reverend the venerable therā in the great wihāra called “king of Māgama,” and 5,000 karīshas from this Padanagala, furnished with have been given over and 4,000 karīshas shall be ; the taxes of the 9,000 karīshas shall be remitted; the rules shall be kept; in the royal family preaching shall be ; this portion of the karīshas now is given; four amunas ; and the remaining portion ; the lords of the Bhikshu congregation shall be caused to be furnished with the four pratyayas; having done this in order that what is given to our uncle the parumaka may be kept, causing it to be written on this stone slab, we have it given.

(77.) Piligāma:—Hail! To the villages Uṭara and Mahagawaṭa eight thousand the embankment in the kingdom this ferry great and venerable, the rest having seen six kingdoms, he protected the weak having made a paddy field six karīshas and six ammanas in circumference, we give to the priesthood in the rana wihāra the four pratyayas.

(85.) Diyagāma:—Hail! Mahakaḍaka spake: A lay devotee his father spake and Caraka’s father Tambucaraka the ferry and the paddy field one pata (in circumference) and Tambuḍaka six karīshas and thirteen paddy fields.

(97.) Nāgiriḱaṇḍa:—(a) Hail! Weḷunāga the Rukawaewa splendour and glory to the priesthood in the Bamanogiriya wihāra.

(b) I the parumaka and his (?) son the Bamanogiriya temple the tank of the great queen and the Kanugariya tank and the Kabuba tank and the Kaṭinaka tank, altogether four tanks, having seen the embankments to the priesthood of the Bamanogiriya wihāra six and five (?) he gave the karshāpaṇas at the Wataka tank, having seen after having assigned he gave the Bamanogiriya wihāra to the priesthood